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ACUTE MESENTERIC ISCHEMIA DUE TO SMA THROMBOSIS- A CASE report

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INTRODUCTION

Acute mesenteric ischemia usually presents as abdominal pain that is out of proportion in relation to tenderness; persistent vomiting, bloody diarrhea and shock. Sloughing of intestinal mucosa takes 3 hours while infarction of entire bowel thickness occurs in 6 hours. ^{[1]-[3]} CECT abdomen with mesenteric angiography is investigation of choice. If patient has presented after

24-48 hours, gangrene might have already occurred, resection and anastomosis is done majority of cases with removal of vascular block under Doppler guidance or Injection of papaverine. Minimum bowel length required to be retained is 1.2 meters, otherwise the patient will have high mortality due to short bowel syndrome. [4]- [7]

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- **AIMS:**

- To compare the surgical findings in various case scenarios having different presentations, patient factors and time of presentations with SMA thrombosis
- To compare outcomes of surgical intervention in different case scenarios

- **Study design:** Observational and retrospective study

- **Study time:** May'2020 to May'2021

- **Study area:** Sheth L G Hospital, Mani Nagar, Ahmedabad

- **Inclusion criteria:**

- Patient admitted to L G hospital for acute mesenteric ischemia due to SMA thrombosis
- Patient in whom surgical intervention done
- Age above 18 years

- **Exclusion criteria:**

- Patient having small bowel obstruction due to any other cause
- Patient who was not operated

CASE SERIES

CASE-1:

A 38-year-old female patient presented with generalized abdominal pain, fever and vomiting for 4 days. On per abdominal examination, lower abdominal tenderness present with per rectal was normal. AXR was showing multiple air-fluid level and raised WBC counts. CECT was suggestive of gangrenous bowel loops with mesenteric ischemia due to SMA thrombosis. On laparotomy, ileum found to be pre-gangrenous (dusky) with free fluid. Drain kept and no resection done (2nd look laparotomy planned). In postoperative period, patient developed low output fecal fistula and severe wound infection which managed conservatively. 2nd laparotomy was successful with resection and anastomosis. Patient was discharged and wound gaping recovered.

CASE 1 INTRAOPERATIVE PICTURE 1

CASE-2:

A 40-year-old male patient presented with complaint of generalized abdominal pain

with distention, bilious vomiting and obstipation for 1 week. Per abdominal examination had generalized guarding and per rectal was normal. Patient was covid-19 positive 3-4 weeks back. Patient was dehydrated on examination with tachycardia and hypotension. Patient erect abdominal X-ray was showing multiple air fluid levels. WBC counts and S. Amylase levels were raised. CECT was suggestive of complete SMA thrombosis with gangrenous bowel loops and gross free fluid. Patient was resuscitated and laparotomy done. On examination, bowel found to be gangrenous from jejunum to ascending colon. Approximately 10 cm portion of jejunum was retained and jejuno-transverse colon anastomosis done. Patient developed high output enterocutaneous fistula and re-laparotomy done. Duodeno-transverse anastomosis was done.

CASE 2 INTRAOPERATIVE PICTURE

CASE-3:

A 50-year-old female patient presented with complaint of 1 episode of blood in stool with not passing stool in the last 4 days. Patient did not have complaint of abdominal pain or vomiting. On examination, per abdomen was soft and per rectal had impacted stool mixed with blood. Patient was covid-19 positive one month back. Abdominal erect x-ray had air fluid levels with CECT of 1 month back was suggestive of 10mm thrombus at origin of SMA with developed ileal and jejunal collaterals. WBC and D-dimer were raised. Repeat CECT done which was showing mild to moderate free fluid with gangrenous bowel loops. On laparotomy, ileum, ascending colon and part of proximal transverse colon was ischemic. Resection of ischemic bowel done and proximal ileum brought as stoma. On pod 4, stoma found to be necrosed and drain having fecal matter. Re-exploration was done and further jejunum was resected keeping proximal 7-10 cm of jejunum. Jejuno- transverse resection and anastomosis was done. In postoperative period patient was having septicemia and DIC. Death occurred at pod 3.

CASE 3 INTRAOPERATIVE PICTURE

CASE-4:

A 55-year-old female patient presented with c/o. Upper abdominal pain and vomiting with passing stool regularly and no complaint of constipation or blood or greenish stool. AXR was showing free gas under diaphragm. CECT was suggestive of SMA thrombus with mild to moderate luminal narrowing. On laparotomy, approximately 15 cm portion of jejunum found to be having ischemic changes with perforation. The diseased portion of jejunum was resected and end to end jejuno-jejunal anastomosis was done. Postoperative period was uneventful.

CASE 4 INTRAOPERATIVE PICTURE

CASE-5:

An 85-year-old female patient presented with complaint of mild generalized abdominal pain since 1 week with no vomiting or constipation. Patient was a k/c/o HTN in the last 8 years. On examination, patient was having pr 100/min and BP 104/70mmhg per abdomen was soft non-tender. On AXR few air fluid levels seen and CECT s/o. severe stenosis with patent lumen of SMA (80-90% narrowing). Celiac trunk and IMA were normal. No free fluid. Patient planned for diagnostics copy. On examination, part of terminal ileum found to be having developing changes of ischemia with no gangrenous bowel segments. Resection and anastomosis were done and postoperative period was uneventful.

CASE 5 INTRAOPERATIVE PICTURE

CASE-6:

A 52-year-old female patient presented with complaint of severe generalized abdominal pain and vomiting in the last 1 day, no complaint of constipation. Patient had encountered covid-19 infection a month back. At presentation patient was having pr 150/min and bp-70/40mmhg. Patient was admitted as acute small bowel obstruction and resuscitated. D-dimer 1200, WBC 11k and creatinine 2.5. Plain CT abdomen was suggestive of, multiple dilated small bowel loops with air fluid levels; multiple conglomerated ileal loops in pelvis. On laparotomy, jejunum ileum and ascending colon found to be having ischemic changes with gangrenous distal ileum. Duodeno-transverse colon end to end anastomosis was done. Patient died at pod 3.

CASE 6 INTRAOPERATIVE PICTURE

OBSERVATIONS

In our case series, 6 patients with acute mesenteric ischemia were managed surgically.

- 2 patients who presented and diagnosed in early stage could be salvaged due to involvement of short bowel segments.
- 3 patients developed enterocutaneous fistula. Who underwent re-laparotomy.
- All patients were proven COVID 19 RTPCR negative, but they all had high D-dimer values with presentation during COVID-19 pandemic. (Though it isn't proven correlation)
- 5 out of 6 were females (Although there is no proven gender predilection)
- Most common complaints of 5 cases were sudden onset of abdominal pain with or without

vomiting. Abdominal distension/ Constipation was not seen in all cases.

- Out of 6 cases, 3 patients had COVID-19 infection one month back.

Authors view: COVID-19 coagulopathy is well known condition which is a hypercoagulable state that predisposes to venous, arterial and small vessel thrombosis. If mesenteric vessels are involved, such conditions present with acute small bowel obstruction. WBC counts are usually raised associated with raised CRP and D-dimer. Immediate anticoagulation with surgical intervention is lifesaving but mortality is high. Heparin or LMWH are to be started for anticoagulation along with antibiotic coverage. Early diagnosis is a key to successful outcome.

Table-1. comparison of findings

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
	38yr/F	40yr/M	50yr/F	55yr/F	85yr/F	52yr/F
Clinical picture	Lower abdominal pain, vomiting	Generalized abdominal pain, distension	1 episode of blood in stool; obstipation in the last 7 days; no abdominal pain/ vomiting	Epigastric pain, vomiting	Asymptomatic	Generalized abdominal pain, vomiting
Any co-morbidity	nil	nil	k/c/o. HTN	nil	K/c/o. DM, HTN	nil
COVID-19 history	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES
Significant laboratory investigations	d-dimer-500	1200	2400	628	595	1200
	CRP- (+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
	TLC-15k	20k	12k	11k	13k	11k
AXR/ CT	Multiple air fluid levels, CECT not done	CECT s/o. gangrenous bowel loops and complete SMA block	AXR multiple air fluid levels; CT angiography- 10mm thrombus at origin of SMA	AXR- Free gas under diaphragm; Ct angiography- SMA thrombus with mild to moderate luminal narrowing	SMA thrombosis with severe luminal narrowing (80-90%); Air fluid levels on AXR	Multiple air fluid levels;
Surgical procedure	Resection of ischemic	Gangrenous jejunum and ileum	Resection of gangrenous	Ischemic portion of jejunum	10cm portion of jejunum	Duodeno - transvers

	ileum and anastomosis	resection	s jejunum, ileum and ascending colon	with perforation resected and anastomosis done	found to be having gangrenous chances, resection and anastomosis done	e anastomosis done
Evolution	Low output fistula and wound infection on POD-5; recovered; Favorable follow-up	Enterocutaneous fistula on POD-4; re-laparotomy done; duodeno-transverse anastomosis; again, EC fistula developed; death on POD 5	Patient developed respiratory infection and septicemia; Death on POD 3	uneventful	Uneventful	Death on Pod 3
Postoperative stay	38	9	3	14	15	3

CONCLUSION

SMA thrombosis was seen in non-covid time as well. Hypercoagulable state which corresponds to raised d-dimer and FDP, the cases of mesenteric ischemia due to SMA thrombosis are seen more commonly in covid-19 era. This series draws to attention that timely diagnosis and appropriate surgery with resection and proper follow up with anti-coagulant the morbidity and mortality is averted. Acute mesenteric ischemia is commonly due to emboli (45-50%) rather than thrombosis (20-25%). Non occlusive disease (5-15%) can be due to various causes e.g., pancreatitis, sepsis, heart failure, etc. Early diagnosis is the key to successful management. Aggressive resuscitation, early revascularization with vascular intervention and exploratory laparotomy is done if evidence of peritonitis is present.^{[8]-[9]} Postoperative fluid management due to short bowel syndrome and appropriate antibiotic coverage is necessary to revive the patient. Long term TPN support for patients with short bowel patients is necessary. They are candidates for intestinal transplantation if survived.^[10]

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